

CURRENT TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BUSINESS PRODUCTS AND SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY FORMATION

Khasanov Sokhibjon

Master of Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: The present article shows that in the conditions of formation of digital economy on an international scale, the creation and continuous improvement of information products and services for all sectors and spheres of the economy, including bines, is of greater importance. The article shows that the development of the information component of economic objects is the basis of their competitiveness in the global economic market.

Keywords: digitalization, information products and services, competitiveness, efficiency, software products, optimization, digital transformation, e-commerce.

Introduction

Over the past two decades, most of the information activities of developed countries have become a major element of market infrastructure and have been embedded in the structure of market relations. Although the formation of the information and communication market as a market infrastructure began in the second half of the 1950s, the structural changes of the last 10 years have turned this sector into a strategic economic force. Today, this market sector is considered the basic foundation of the national economy of each country. Because the development of the world economy requires a modern information and communication infrastructure. In developed countries, their economic growth is driven by information, knowledge and intellectual potential. Information and software products - the basis for the development of economic objects in the conditions of digital transformation

As the world practice shows, the world's largest research institutions in the field of ICT (ITU, Gartner Research, IICD, JB infoDev program, UNESCAP) in the field of processes of formation of digital economy, index of economic development and ICT consumption, measurement of the impact of knowledge and innovation, efficiency of AMH research works. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also conducting a whole range of research in such areas as efficiency of investments in ICT, e-

government, e-commerce, information society, creation of innovative types of information and software products and services. In this regard, it is important to study methodological aspects of the development of information products and services business in our country.

The development of information products and services business provides economic development and growth in many ways. That is why developed and developing countries of the world try to develop ICT business and create new types of AMX. The largest and most profitable software companies of the world are located in the USA, 65 out of 100 largest software companies of the world, announced by "Top 100 Research Foundation" in 2010, are located there. In terms of the number of companies, Japan and France ranked second and third (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Geographic location of the world's top 100 information products companies.

In terms of exports of software products and related services, India has been leading the global market for several years now. In this regard, Ireland and China ranked second and third respectively.

India entered the global software export market in the early 1990s. According to Nasscom, the software industry grew 58% between 2007 and 2013, accounting for

6.5% of India's total ICT outsourcing in 2009. By 2016, annual exports in India's ICT outsourcing industry totaled \$155.2 billion. More than two million people are employed in this industry, accounting for more than USD. Companies in the United States and the European Union can be called the main buyers of Indian programmers' services.

Conclusion

In recent years, the analysis of global economic indicators related to the information society shows that there are trends of a natural increase in the share of information products and services in the national economies of developed and developing countries. From these analyses, it can be concluded that while the emphasis is on the innovation economy, the economies of countries are growing at the expense of information products and services, and this sector is the basis of the innovation economy. The development of the information products and services sector on a proper scientific basis and based on the experience applied in developed countries serves the formation of information society and innovation economy in the country. It should be taken into account that the development of entrepreneurship and business processes in this sphere is impossible without a thorough analysis of structural aspects of information products and services, without taking into account modern trends, without studying its specific aspects. In this respect, studying unique and important aspects of our country, identifying problems and finding solutions on their basis is the key to tomorrow's development.

REFERENCE:

1. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on the most important priority tasks for 2019 from December 28, 2018. Portal of the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan (www.uza.uz).
2. Abdurakhmonova G.K. "Modern World: Social Networks Manage Human Resources" Tashkent.2021 -86 p.
3. www.lex.uz - national database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
www.ziynet.uz - educational portal.
4. <https://regulation.gov.uz/uz/document/3085>

5. Набижонов, О., Шавкатова, Ш. ., & Сатторова , С. . (2022). КОРХОНАЛАРДА ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ ХАРАЖАТЛАРИНИ МИНИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ СТРАТЕГИЯСИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук, 2(7), 27–29. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/EJLFAS/article/view/1918>

6. Otabek Ganiyevich Nabijonov, & Sh. A. Kholbutaeva (2022). THE ROLE OF CONSULTING IN THE MODERN MARKET ECONOMY. Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, 2 (2), 5-8.

7. Ugli, A. S. O., Ganiyevich, N. O., Ugli, Y. S. Z., & Ugli, K. R. A. (2021). About how cheap (actually very expensive) loans may not enrich the poor. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 2191-2193.

8. Shavkatova , S. ., & Nabijonov , O. . (2022). INNOVATSIYA FAOLIYATINING ANAMIYATI. Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук, 2(11), 4–7. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/EJLFAS/article/view/4088>

9. Отабек Ганиевич Набижонов, Зоҳиджон Раббимкул Ўғли Хужамкулов, and Ф. Б. Шакирова. "ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР НЕГИЗИДА БАРҚАРОР ИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ" Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, vol. 2, no. 4, 2022, pp. 326-334.

10. Nabijonov Otabek Ganiyevich (2021). IQTISODIYOTDA RAQOVATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI. Scientific progress, 1 (3), 136-139.

11. Otabek Ganiyevich Nabijonov, Shokhzod Otabek ugli Abdurazzokov, Sanjarbek Zokhidjon ugli Yuldashaliyev Academic research in modern science 1 (1), 220-222, 2022

12. Nabijonov, O. G., ugli Abdurazzokov, S. O., & ugli Yuldashaliyev, S. Z. (2022). DO WE WANT TO LIBERALIZE TRADE OR VICE VERSA. Academic research in modern science, 1(1), 220-222.